

Identifying EarthScope

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The goal of a connected global ecosystem of research results, datasets, people, and organizations has been on the table since before Berners-Lee coined the expression “Linked Open Data” during the early 2000s. Progress toward that goal is accelerating, aided by the emergence of open persistent identifiers for many kinds of research objects (DOIs), people (ORCIDs), and organizations (RORs). A graph built using these identifiers and related connections, the PID Graph, was introduced during 2019 and DataCite introduced the DataCite Commons, a discovery service built on this emerging graph, during 2020. Many capabilities have been added to the DataCite Commons since 2020 and other tools based to some extent on the PID Graph concept, e.g. [OpenAlex](#) or [ResearchGraph](#), have emerged. Together they form an expanding collection of powerful capabilities for understanding the research landscape and connection-based discovery of research resources.

The U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF) supports major facilities that are critical global infrastructure for many important research fields and persistent identifiers are the critical ticket for these organizations into the PID connected world. Searches of DataCite Commons can provide insights into how some of these organizations are currently participating in the PID Graph. Figure 1 shows the number of DOIs discovered by searching the DataCite Commons using organizational identifiers (RORs) for NSF major facilities. This Figure includes those facilities with less than 1,000 resources discovered in this way (the NSF Geodetic Facility for the Advancement of Geoscience (GAGE) and NSF Seismological Facility for the Advancement of Geoscience (SAGE) Facilities, operated by EarthScope Consortium, have more than 100,000 resources and are discussed below). Most of the DOIs discovered for these facilities are registered with DataCite (blue) and most are datasets. Resources registered with Crossref (tan) are mostly journal articles.

It is important to keep in mind that this is a measure of the number of resources that include facility RORs in their metadata rather than the number of published resources (datasets or journal articles) that are related to these facilities.

Facilities associated with the EarthScope Consortium have more than 100,000 resources discovered through DataCite Commons. These organizations have a long history of using persistent identifiers (DOIs) from DataCite for datasets. They also reflect the recent transition from two separate facilities: the NSF GAGE Facility (operated by UNAVCO) and the NSF SAGE Facility (operated by the Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology, (IRIS)), now both operated by the EarthScope Consortium. This Tech Note describes some early results from an on-going project focused on improving utilization of identifiers in their DataCite metadata.

Figure 1. Number of resources (Crossref and DataCite DOIs) discovered searching the DataCite Commons using NSF Facility RORs. This Figure includes facilities with fewer than 1,000 DOIs. Facilities related to EarthScope, with 100,000+ resources are discussed below.

Minting New Identifiers

The first step in the project was to create identifiers for two new facilities as UNAVCO became the Geodetic Facility for the Advancement of Geoscience (GAGE) and IRIS became the Seismological Facility for the Advancement of Geoscience (SAGE). We worked with ror.org to create metadata for these two organizations and then created the relationships required for users to understand how everything fits together. IRIS and UNAVCO were flagged as “predecessor organizations” to EarthScope that were no longer active, while GAGE (<https://ror.org/03c1c5b19>) and SAGE (<https://ror.org/057py8t43>), with new RORs, were identified as children “NSF facilities” of both the operator, EarthScope Consortium (<https://ror.org/04danrt76>), and the U.S. National Science Foundation.

Once the new identifiers were in place, we began the process of updating the DataCite metadata. Figure 2 illustrates the transition between these identifiers that has occurred between February (blue) and July (purple) of 2025. The legacy identifiers, near the bottom of the Figure, show significant decreases in occurrence as they were replaced with the new identifiers shown near the top of the Figure.

Figure 2. Evolution of EarthScope identifiers during 2025. The blue dots and numbers are identifier counts during February 2025, and the purple dots are identifier counts during July 2025. The two legacy identifiers at the bottom show large decreases while the more recent identifiers at the top show increases. Note that the SAGE and GAGE identifiers did not exist during February, so they were not counted at that time.

Iterative Metadata Improvement

The primary DataCite use case is resource identification and citation, and six elements required for that use case continue to be the [mandatory](#) DataCite elements. Historically, the UNAVCO and IRIS metadata have focused on these mandatory elements. The DataCite Metadata Schema includes over 60 elements that can support many different metadata use cases. In this work we focus on four use cases that support the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable): FAIR Text, FAIR Identifiers, FAIR Connections, and FAIR Contacts ([Habermann, 2025](#)). Improving utilization of elements supporting these use cases is the goal of our iterative metadata improvement project.

Figure 3. Metadata completeness is visualized using a radar plot with metadata elements around the outside and completeness going from 0% at the center of the plots to 100% at the edge. These plots make it easy to identify accomplishments and opportunities for improvement.

Measuring Improvement

We measure completeness of metadata elements that are related to these four use cases to demonstrate improvement. Completeness is visualized using a radar plot (Figure 3) with metadata elements around the edge and completeness going from zero at the middle of the plot to 100% on the edge.

Current Progress

Metadata improvements can be visualized using a series of radar plot snapshots through time (Figure 4). The rows in this Figure show results for the four use cases at two times ([see detailed use case descriptions and radar plot keys](#)). The initial baselines reflect mandatory fields required for DataCite metadata that are concentrated in the FAIR Text use case in the top row of Figure 4. The metadata has been improved in a series of re-curation steps,

adding author affiliations, author, affiliation and publisher identifiers, and data license/rights information. The current metadata supports all four use cases, increasing completeness for FAIR Identifiers, FAIR Connections, and FAIR Contacts by between 11 and 40%. The overall completeness increased from < 15% to over 30% for both repositories. Ongoing work is focused on finding and adding more identifiers for researchers, affiliated organizations, funders, and awards.

Figure 4. GAGE and SAGE metadata completeness for four FAIR use cases. Each row provides results for a use case at two times. The completeness for each use case is shown below the radar plots. The initial baselines, shown in dashed boxes, show only the mandatory DataCite fields and total completeness < 15% for each repository. Iterative improvement added affiliations, identifiers, and licenses to the metadata to increase overall completeness to over 25%.

Other Facilities

Six of the facilities shown in Figure 1 are already using DataCite for dataset DOIs and associated metadata. Metadata for these repositories were retrieved and measured using the tools described above. The overall completeness for these repositories is listed in Table 1. The EarthScope re-curation efforts have increased completeness for their metadata into the range of these other facilities.

Table 1. Number of records and overall metadata completeness for eight NSF facilities that are currently using DataCite for DOIs.

Organization	#	Completeness
National Solar Observatory (cub.nso)	9	26%
Ocean Observatories Initiative Data (hain.njltcl)	75	37%
Texas A&M University International Ocean Discovery (tdl.iodp)	820	24%
National Ecological Observatory Network (neon.prod)	637	38%
UCAR / NCAR (ucar.ucar)	3106	21%
NCAR Earth Observing Laboratory (ucar.eol)	8762	37%
Geodetic Facility for the Advancement of Geoscience (unavco.unavco)	6347	Baseline: 14%, Current: 32%
Seismological Facility for the Advancement of Geoscience (iris.iris)	117590	Baseline: 11%, Current: 37%

Figure 5 shows more details of the completeness for these repositories for each of the four use cases ([detailed use case descriptions and radar plot keys](#)). Like the EarthScope baselines shown in Figure 4, the FAIR Text use case that includes mandatory fields is the most complete for all these facilities. The other use cases have broader ranges of completeness and show repositories with more complete metadata, bright spots (green), that can serve as good examples for other repositories that are working to improve their metadata completeness.

Figure 5. Metadata completeness for four FAIR use cases at eight NSF facilities. Repositories with outstanding completeness, termed bright spots (shown by green boxes), exist for each use case. These repositories can serve as good examples and sources of lessons learned for re-curation efforts in other repositories.

Conclusion

During the last several years identifiers for research objects, people, and organizations have emerged as important elements for identification and citation of research objects and for creating persistent and unambiguous connections across the growing global research infrastructure.

Several NSF facilities are participating in this global effort by using DOIs to identify datasets and other kinds of research objects their communities produce. Most of this work has focused on minimal metadata, i.e. the mandatory fields required for minting a DOI. The DOI metadata includes many recommended and optional fields that can be used to support other use cases. An ongoing effort at EarthScope demonstrates how these other metadata elements can be populated to take advantage of the broader capabilities of existing metadata records in these repositories.

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